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Geometry of masses of material sets from the point of view of the neutrosophic logic

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Abstract: In this paper we discuss the geometry of the masses of the neutrosophic material point and material sets according to the neutrosophic logic. First, we discuss the moments of inertia and the products of inertia of the neutrosophic material point and the relating theorems from the point of view of neutrosophic logic. Then, we generalized the above-mentioned results to the neutrosophic material sets. Finally, we end the paper by suggesting some problems for discussing.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Logic, Geometry of Masses, Moments of Inertia, Products of Inertia, Classical Mechanics

Introduction

In [20] the two-dimensional motion of a neutrosophic material point is discussed. In [21] the kinetic elements (momentum, angular momentum, kinetic energy) of a neutrosophic material point in its two-dimensional motion are also discussed. In [22] The space of Galilean events, the inertial frames and the Galilean group of transformations for the classical mechanics were discussed according to the neutrosophic logic.

1. Materials and Methods (proposed work with more details)

We will use the geometry proposed by Florentin Smarandacheş and Ahmed Salama [1-19], the definition of the neutrosophic material point proposed in [20,21], and the result of [22] in order to discuss the geometry of masses for a material point and material sets from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

Our results are discussed the follows:

Definition.1: (Moments of inertia of a material point from the point of view of the neutrosophic logic): Let $OXYZ$ be a neutrosophic comparison frame of origin $O = O_1 + I O_2$ and base $(\vec{I}, \vec{J}, \vec{K})$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{I} &= \vec{i}_1 + I \left(\frac{\vec{i}_1 + \vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}} - \vec{i}_1 \right) \\ \vec{J} &= \vec{j}_1 + I \left(\frac{\vec{j}_1 + \vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}} - \vec{j}_1 \right) \\ \vec{K} &= \vec{k}_1 + I \left(\frac{\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}} - \vec{k}_1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

in which: $\vec{i}_1, \vec{i}_2, \vec{j}_1, \vec{j}_2, \vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2$ are traditional unit vectors, and $\vec{i}_1 \perp \vec{i}_2, \vec{j}_1 \perp \vec{j}_2, \vec{k}_1 \perp \vec{k}_2$, and each of triple $(\vec{i}_1, \vec{j}_1, \vec{k}_1), \left(\frac{\vec{i}_1 + \vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{j}_1 + \vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$ are orthonormal and directly oriented. Let $M(X, Y, Z)$ be a neutrosophic material point where:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= x_1 + I x_2 \\ Y &= y_1 + I y_2 \\ Z &= z_1 + I z_2 \end{aligned}$$

with mass $m = m_1 + I m_2$ and time $t = t_1 + I t_2$ and position vector:

$$\vec{r} = \vec{r}_1 + I \vec{r}_2 = \overline{OM} = X\vec{I} + Y\vec{J} + Z\vec{K}$$

We call the non-negative quantity $I_0 = m r^2$, (where $r^2 = \vec{r} \cdot \vec{r}$), the moment of inertia of the material point M with respect to O from the point of view of the neutrosophic logic.

Definitions.2:

- We call the non-negative quantity $I_{OXY} = mZ^2$ the moment of inertia of the material point M with respect to the plane OXY from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.
- We call the non-negative quantity $I_{OYZ} = mX^2$ the moment of inertia of the material point M with respect to the plane OYZ from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.
- We call the non-negative quantity $I_{OXZ} = mY^2$ the moment of inertia of the material point M with respect to the plane OXZ from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

Definition3:

- We call the non-negative quantity $I_{OX} = m(Y^2 + Z^2)$ the moment of inertia of material point M with respect to the OX axis from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.
- We call the non-negative quantity $I_{OY} = m(X^2 + Z^2)$ the moment of inertia of material point M with respect to the OY axis from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.
- We call the non-negative quantity $I_{OZ} = m(X^2 + Y^2)$ the moment of inertia of the material point M with respect to the OZ axis from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

Results (I):

We note that:

1-

$$I_o = \frac{1}{2}[I_{Ox} + I_{Oy} + I_{Oz}]$$

2-

$$I_o = I_{Oxy} + I_{Oxz} + I_{Oyz}$$

3-

$$I_{Ox} = I_{Oxy} + I_{Oxz}$$

4-

$$I_{Oy} = I_{Oxy} + I_{Oyz}$$

5-

$$I_{Oz} = I_{Oxz} + I_{Oyz}$$

6-

$$I_o = I_{Oz} + I_{Oxy}$$

7-

$$I_o = I_{Ox} + I_{Oyz}$$

8-

$$I_o = I_{Oy} + I_{Oxz}$$

Theorem1: The I_o is equivalent to two traditional moments of inertia:

the first $I_{O_1} = m_1(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2)$ in the traditional space \mathbb{R}^3 with the base $(\vec{i}_1, \vec{j}_1, \vec{k}_1)$ and origin O_1 . The second: $I_{O_2} = (m_1 + m_2)[(x_1 + x_2)^2 + (y_1 + y_2)^2 + (z_1 + z_2)^2]$ in the traditional space \mathbb{R}^3

with the base is $(\frac{\vec{i}_1 + \vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{j}_1 + \vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}})$ and origin $O = O_1 + O_2$.

Proof:

We start from the relationship:

$$\begin{aligned} I_o &= m(X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2) = (m_1 + Im_2)[(x_1 + Ix_2)^2 + (y_1 + Iy_2)^2 + (z_1 + Iz_2)^2] \\ &= (m_1 + Im_2)[x_1^2 + 2Ix_1x_2 + Ix_2^2 + y_1^2 + 2Iy_1y_2 + Iy_2^2 + z_1^2 + 2Iz_1z_2 \\ &\quad + Iz_2^2] \\ &= (m_1 + Im_2)[(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2) + I(x_2^2 + y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2x_1x_2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2)] \\ &= m_1(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2) \\ &\quad + I[m_1(x_2^2 + y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2x_1x_2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2) + m_2(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2) \\ &\quad + m_2(x_2^2 + y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2x_1x_2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2)] \end{aligned}$$

Now, by applying isometric transformation:

$$T: \mathbb{R}(I) \mapsto \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}$$

$$A = a_1 + Ia_2 \mapsto (a_1, a_1 + a_2)$$

we find:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T(I_O) &= [m_1(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2), m_1(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2) + m_1(x_2^2 + y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2x_1x_2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2) \\
 &\quad + m_2(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2) + m_2(x_2^2 + y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2x_1x_2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2)] \\
 &= [m_1(x_1^2 + y_1^2 + z_1^2), (m_1 + m_2)[(x_1 + x_2)^2 + (y_1 + y_2)^2 + (z_1 + z_2)^2]] = (I_{O_1}, I_{\hat{O}})
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Theorem2: The I_{O_X} is equivalent to two traditional moments of inertia:

the first $I_{O_1x_1} = m_1(y_1^2 + z_1^2)$ in the traditional space \mathbb{R}^3 with the base $(\vec{i}_1, \vec{j}_1, \vec{k}_1)$ and origin O_1 ;
 the second $I_{\hat{O}\hat{x}} = (m_1 + m_2)[(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (z_1 + z_2)^2]$,(where: $\hat{O} = O_1 + O_2$, and $\hat{x} = x_1 + x_2$) in the
 traditional space \mathbb{R}^3 with base $(\frac{\vec{i}_1+\vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{j}_1+\vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{k}_1+\vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}})$ and origin \hat{O} .

Proof:

We start from the relationship:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{O_X} &= m(Y^2 + Z^2) = (m_1 + Im_2)[(y_1 + Iy_2)^2 + (z_1 + Iz_2)^2] = \\
 &= (m_1 + Im_2)[(y_1^2 + z_1^2) + I(y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2)] \\
 &= m_1(y_1^2 + z_1^2) \\
 &\quad + I[m_1(y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2) + m_2(y_1^2 + z_1^2) \\
 &\quad + m_2(y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2)]
 \end{aligned}$$

By applying isometric transformation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T: \mathbb{R}(I) &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \\
 A = a_1 + Ia_2 &\mapsto (a_1, a_1 + a_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

on both sides of the previous relationship, we find:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T(I_{O_X}) &= [m_1(y_1^2 + z_1^2), m_1(y_1^2 + z_1^2) + m_1(y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2) + m_2(y_1^2 + z_1^2) \\
 &\quad + m_2(y_2^2 + z_2^2 + 2y_1y_2 + 2z_1z_2)] \\
 &= \{ m_1(y_1^2 + z_1^2), (m_1 + m_2)[(y_1 + y_2)^2 + (z_1 + z_2)^2] \} = (I_{O_1x_1}, I_{\hat{O}\hat{x}})
 \end{aligned}$$

and this completes the proof.

Theorem3: The $I_{O_{XY}}$ is equivalent to two traditional moments of inertia:

the first $I_{O_1x_1y_1} = m_1z_1^2$ in the traditional space \mathbb{R}^3 with the base $(\vec{i}_1, \vec{j}_1, \vec{k}_1)$ and origin O_1 ; the
 second $I_{\hat{O}\hat{x}\hat{y}} = (m_1 + m_2)(z_1 + z_2)^2$,(where $\hat{O} = O_1 + O_2$, $\hat{x} = x_1 + x_2$ and $\hat{y} = y_1 + y_2$) , in the
 traditional space \mathbb{R}^3 with the base $(\frac{\vec{i}_1+\vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{j}_1+\vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{k}_1+\vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}})$ and the origin \hat{O} .

Proof:

We start from the relationship:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{O_{XY}} &= mZ^2 = (m_1 + Im_2)(z_1 + Iz_2)^2 == (m_1 + Im_2)[z_1^2 + 2Iz_1z_2 + z_2^2] \\
 &= m_1z_1^2 + I[m_1z_2^2 + 2m_1z_1z_2 + m_2z_1^2 + m_2z_2^2 + 2m_2z_1z_2]
 \end{aligned}$$

By applying isometric transformation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 T: \mathbb{R}(I) &\rightarrow \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \\
 A = a_1 + Ia_2 &\mapsto (a_1, a_1 + a_2)
 \end{aligned}$$

on both sides of the previous relationship, we find:

$$T(I_{OXY}) = [m_1z_1^2, m_1z_1^2 + m_1z_2^2 + 2m_1z_1z_2 + m_2z_1^2 + m_2z_2^2 + 2m_2z_1z_2] = [m_1z_1^2, (m_1 + m_2)(z_1 + z_2)^2] = (I_{O_1x_1y_1}, I_{\acute{O}\acute{x}\acute{y}})$$

and this completes the proof.

In the same way, we can arrive to following similar results for:

- a) $I_{OY} \simeq I_{OZ}$
- b) $I_{OYZ} \simeq I_{OXZ}$

Definition4: (Inertial products of material point):

Consider the neutrosophic comparison frame $OXYZ$ of origin $O = O_1 + I O_2$ and base $(\vec{I}, \vec{J}, \vec{K})$, where:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{I} &= \vec{i}_1 + I \left(\frac{\vec{i}_1 + \vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}} - \vec{i}_1 \right) \\ \vec{J} &= \vec{j}_1 + I \left(\frac{\vec{j}_1 + \vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}} - \vec{j}_1 \right) \\ \vec{K} &= \vec{k}_1 + I \left(\frac{\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}} - \vec{k}_1 \right) \end{aligned}$$

in which: $\vec{i}_1, \vec{i}_2, \vec{j}_1, \vec{j}_2, \vec{k}_1, \vec{k}_2$ are traditional unit vectors, and $\vec{i}_1 \perp \vec{i}_2, \vec{j}_1 \perp \vec{j}_2, \vec{k}_1 \perp \vec{k}_2$, and each of triple $(\vec{I}, \vec{J}, \vec{K}), \left(\frac{\vec{i}_1 + \vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{j}_1 + \vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}} \right)$ are orthonormal and directly oriented. Let $M(X, Y, Z)$ be a neutrosophic material point, where:

$$\begin{aligned} X &= x_1 + Ix_2 \\ Y &= y_1 + Iy_2 \\ Z &= z_1 + Iz_2 \end{aligned}$$

with mass $m = m_1 + Im_2$, and time $t = t_1 + It_2$, and position vector

$$\vec{r} = \vec{r}_1 + I\vec{r}_2 = \vec{OM} = X\vec{I} + Y\vec{J} + Z\vec{K}$$

- We call $P_{XY} = mXY$ the product of inertia of the material point with respect to the tow neutrosophic planes OYZ and OXZ .
- We call $P_{XZ} = mXZ$ the product of inertia of the material point with respect to the tow neutrosophic planes OXY and OYZ .
- We call $P_{YZ} = mYZ$ the product the inertia of the material point with respect to the tow neutrosophic planes OXY and OXZ .

We have the following theorem:

Theorem 4: The product of inertia P_{XY} is equivalent to tow classical products of inertia as follows: the first $P_{x_1y_1} = m_1x_1y_1$ in the traditional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 with the base is $(\vec{i}_1, \vec{j}_1, \vec{k}_1)$ and the origin O_1 . The second $P_{\acute{x}\acute{y}} = (m_1 + m_2)(x_1 + x_2)(y_1 + y_2)$, where

$(\acute{x} = x_1 + x_2, \acute{y} = y_1 + y_2)$ in the traditional space \mathbb{R}^3 with the base $\left(\frac{\vec{i}_1 + \vec{i}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{j}_1 + \vec{j}_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{\vec{k}_1 + \vec{k}_2}{\sqrt{2}} \right)$ and the origin \acute{O} .

Proof:

we have:

$$P_{XY} = mXY = (m_1 + Im_2)(x_1 + Ix_2)(y_1 + Iy_2) = (m_1 + Im_2)[x_1y_1 + I(x_1y_2 + x_2y_1 + x_2y_2)]$$

$$= m_1x_1y_1 + I[m_1(x_1y_2 + x_2y_1 + x_2y_2) + m_2x_1y_1 + m_2(x_1y_2 + x_2y_1 + x_2y_2)]$$

Applying the T isometric transformation to both sides of the previous relationship, we find:

$$T(P_{XY}) = [m_1x_1y_1, m_1x_1y_1 + m_1(x_1y_2 + x_2y_1 + x_2y_2) + m_2x_1y_1 + m_2(x_1y_2 + x_2y_1 + x_2y_2)]$$

$$= [m_1x_1y_1, (m_1 + m_2)(x_1 + x_2)(y_1 + y_2)] = (P_{x_1y_1}, P_{x_2y_2})$$

and this completes the proof.

In the same way, similar results can be proved for P_{XZ} and P_{YZ} .

We also need the following definition:

Definition 5 (Neutrosophic material Set):

we call

$$S = \{[M_i(X^i, Y^i, Z^i), m^i = m^i_1 + Im^i_2, t = t_1 + It_2], i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

a neutrosophic material set with masses $m^i = m^i_1 + Im^i_2$ and time $t = t_1 + It_2$.

Definitions 6: (The moments of inertial of the material set S). Let $OXYZ$ be the same neutrosophic comparison frame considered in the previous definitions.

- We call

$$I_o = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i [(X^i)^2 + (Y^i)^2 + (Z^i)^2]$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the origin O from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

- We call

$$I_{OX} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i [(Y^i)^2 + (Z^i)^2]$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the OX axis from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

- We call

$$I_{OY} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i [(X^i)^2 + (Z^i)^2]$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the OY axis from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

- We call

$$I_{OZ} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i [(X^i)^2 + (Y^i)^2]$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the OZ axis from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

- We call

$$I_{OXY} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i (Z^i)^2$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the plane OXY from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

- We call

$$I_{OYZ} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i (X^i)^2$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the plane OYZ from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

- We call

$$I_{OXZ} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i (Y^i)^2$$

the moment of inertia of the material set S with respect to the plane OXZ from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.

Remark1:

- 1- The results (I) for moments of inertia related to the neutrosophic material point still true for material set S .
- 2- The theorems about moments of inertia of the material point still true for the material set S .

Definition 7: (The products of inertial for material Set S):

- We call $P_{XY} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i X^i Y^i$ the product of inertia of the material set S with respect to the OYZ and OXZ neutrosophic planes.
- We call $P_{YZ} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i Y^i Z^i$ the product of inertia of the material set S with respect to the OYZ and OXZ neutrosophic planes.
- We call $P_{XZ} = \sum_{i=1}^n m^i X^i Z^i$ the product of inertia of the material set S with respect to the OXY and OYZ neutrosophic planes.

Remark2: The theorems about product of inertia for the neutrosophic material point still valid for the neutrosophic material set.

Conclusions

1. Results: In this paper, the moments and products of inertia for a neutrosophic material point and its related properties and theorems were discussed. This result has been generalized to a neutro-sophic material sets.

2. Suggestions:

- 1 - Discuss the center of masses of a material set from the point of view of neutrosophic logic.
- 2- Discussion of the Huygens' first and second theorems for the moments and products of inertia of a neutrosophic material set.
- 3- Generalizing the concept of the coherent material set and the related theorems from the traditional concept to the neutrosophic concept.
- 4- Generalizing the concept of the translatability movement of the coherent material set and related theorems from the traditional logic to the neutrosophic logic.

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